

Analysis of the Scan Path Using Online Newspapers

Path Comparison Between User and Expert

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Abstract

This study examines to what extent, within online newspapers, the user's scan path coincides with the real information behavior found within the newspapers according to the experts. Primary research methods utilized are questionnaires, interviews and eye tracking (concerning scenarios) of user/expert scan paths of the online newspapers. Information obtained through these methods will be compared and contrasted where appropriate to examine the primary purpose of this study.

Keywords: Information behavior, Eye tracking, Scan path

1 Introduction

Reading online newspapers has become a part of our everyday lives. Aside from reading the printed news each day, a large number of people visit online newspapers. The timeliness of delivery and ability to update the online information is a user attraction and benefit of online news. This is a tremendous advantage compared to reading daily print newspapers; however the

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motivations for reading news online can vary greatly throughout the user population: While one person may scan through the news pages to remain aware of the overview provided by TV news, another person may be more interested in entertainment because he is just passing the time. Separate but related to this trend in readable news, is the purpose of the “newspaper” medium to provide useful information for all of its readers. Furthermore, to remain competitive it is a requirement of the “newspaper” approach to satisfy the diversity of information needs found amongst readers.

2 Motivation

Presently, the design of online newspaper newspapers is in the hands of the developers. Designs generally comply with commonly accepted standards, trends in web development and with findings from web research. Often the online user of “newspapers” is not adequately considered regardless of the various information needs or individual situations. Critical within this situation is a much more precise knowledge of the actual user scan path¹ without which, given the variety of search scenarios, a user-friendly presentation of the web page is impossible.

Visiting an online news site is a rather complex information process. Previous eye tracking studies related to online news neglected this dynamic process and were limited to the resulting static web pages. A realistic impression of a user visit to an online newspaper site can be realized through proper experimentation with dynamic user activities.

User scan path analysis includes the recognition of “using types” or “user types”. Identification of the various “types” reading online newspapers is the basis for the development of a more user-friendly approach and also the focus of this study.

A user-friendly design of online newspapers should consider and be oriented on the user. Therefore, the users’ scan path (e.g., according to Nielsen’s F-Shaped Pattern; Nielsen, 2006) is critical to understanding how the user approaches online news sites. With the design dependent on the users’ scan path, it is fundamental to have more information about this behavior.

¹ The eye tracker records the fixations and the saccades of the subject’s gaze while the subject is looking at the screen. The formed sequence is called the scan path.

According to Wartenberg (2005) “[...] designers make assumptions as to how alternative layout options might influence the way the reader is going to perceive [...]”. For design optimization it is important to know if such a path exists and *how* the experts generate any later path. With an expert testing the structure of the online news can be inspected and the design assumptions of the experts can be evaluated.

In summary, the emphasis is on the examination of information behavior while reading online news in different given scenarios. The study will highlight whether an ideal common user scan path (depending on the scenario) remains and whether there are types of users or using included. Additionally, conclusions will be drawn as to whether this ideal path regarding the user “types” correlate with the planned experts’ described path. Finally, the extent to which the experts’ idea of the user’s scan path coincides with the real information behavior on online newspapers is to be examined in greater detail.

3 State of the art

Newspapers in their traditional print form have been the subject of numerous studies for a long time: Garcia (1991) published the first findings of information behavior with scan paths in English newspapers. Also Küpper (1989) analyzed German newspapers concerning the effects and influences of various elements (pictures, color, headlines, etc.). They specifically attempted to figure out which element is the point of entry. Since the first newspapers were available on the Internet, research dealt with this new and evolving format (e.g. Lewenstein, 2000). On the one hand the new format was analyzed by comparing the “old” print format with the new online version. While on the other hand the same questions arose regarding the information behavior in printed newspapers. Outing (2004) changed the focus to the identification of potential scan paths on web pages through the use of eye tracking. They checked the effectiveness of homepage layouts by identifying how news websites looked through the readers’ eyes.

A concrete comparison between user behavior and the experts’ view first appeared in a study by Holmqvist (2005). This comparison was focused only on printed news. This study of the information behavior in online newspapers “the path designed by the experts for the user” is often mentioned. Presently,

this path has not been demonstrated nor has the comparison between user and expert been analyzed for online newspapers.

4 Approach

The design of an online newspaper is based on the conception of a developer team. They pursue the goal to create a web page as user-friendly as possible. Holmqvist (2005) mentions that developer create a web page in such a manner that the user follows their given scan path. This conception of a scan path is the crucial factor for the web design in order to reach a maximum usability.

The existing web site of the local newspaper "Mittelbayerische Zeitung" will provide the study vehicle for this examination. An analysis of the most visited German online newspapers shows that this site contains the prevailing presentation concepts for German online news. The pivotal factor in choosing this newspaper is the previously unreleased new appearance of this newspaper and therefore non-biased subjects. One established method to identify user information behavior on web pages is eye tracking. This method enables researchers to track the users' scan path and, if possible, identify path patterns. The scan paths of the user in this study are recorded with a static eye tracker.

The emphasis of this study is placed on the comparison between the experts and the user paths. The study will have to consider the experts and the users in a manner that will yield reasoned conclusions. The expert group will include a team of developers, usability experts and also experts for newspaper design. Because of the feasibility and the complexity of the eye tracking study, the user group was reduced to get a non-representative but homogeneous focus group. The newspaper agencies called the readers between 19 and 30 years of age their main target group. For the eye tracking study 30 students were tested.

To obtain a realistic view of the information behavior in online newspapers all areas of use have to be considered. With the aid of questionnaires and interviews, the four areas of use were defined as news, fields of interest, investigation and entertainment based on the findings of Bucher (2003) and Spott (1998). According to Borlund (2003) reliable data should be generated by involving scenarios. For this reason an eye tracking study was organized

to include all these four areas of use each with a specific scenario (first one static, the following ones dynamic and randomized).

5 Outlook

Before raising the gaze paths of the expert group the eye tracking data of the user has to be analyzed. First the relationship between the different elements (e.g. picture, text or headline) will be annotated and analyzed. Then the scan paths of existing types of users and using will be examined. An attempt will be made to find patterns within and overall the scenarios and also patterns in using specific concepts (e.g. welcome page).

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